

PRODUCTION OF THE JOSHI EFFECT IN OXYGEN UNDER SILENT
ELECTRIC DISCHARGE. PART VI. INFLUENCE OF THE
EXCITING POTENTIAL, THE GAS PRESSURE AND THE
MATERIAL OF THE CENTRAL H.T., UNDER SEMI-
OZONISER EXCITATION

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The Joshi effect Δi has been studied in oxygen in the range 10-500 mm. Hg (p) and excited over 0.5 to 4 kilo-volts (V) of 50 cycles frequency in semi-ozonisers with Pt, Au, Ag and Cu central H.T. electrodes. The 'threshold potential' V_m is sensibly a linear function of p . Δi sets in near V_m . Above V_m , the net effect Δi at constant p first increases with V and then decreases. The relative effect % Δi is a maximum near V_m , and diminishes thereafter. Δi increases with p up to a limiting pressure and then decreases. These results are similar to those observed for the gas in Siemens' tubes. Δi is influenced by the nature of the central H.T. This is traced to the differences in the photo-electric activity of the chemically adsorbed layers of oxygen.

It was observed by Joshi (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, pp. 70-75) that the above effect Δi occurs to more than a detectible extent in chlorine subjected to ionisation by collision in wire-in-cylinder type discharge tubes or semi-ozonisers. Apart from this, all previous work on this phenomenon referred chiefly to the Siemens' tube as the excited system. The present work, which is an extension of the preliminary investigations of the author (Mohanty, *ibid.*, 1948, Part III, *Chem. Sec.*, Abst. No. 36), refers to variation with the applied potential V, the gas pressure p , and the material of the central H.T. electrode of the Joshi effect in oxygen under semi-ozoniser excitation.

EXPERIMENTAL

The general assemblage of apparatus and the experimental procedure were essentially similar to those described in Part I (Mohanty and Kamath, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 405). Four semi-ozonisers (Fig. 1) of equal dimensions* and designated W, X, Y and Z were used; the central H.T. electrodes were respectively of platinum, gold, silver and copper. The low tension electrode in each case was represented by a helix of bright-copper wire (the distance between consecutive turns being sufficiently large to permit irradiation of the enclosed gas) on the outer (glass) tube. The discharge current i was observed with a sensitive mirror galvanometer G actuated by a Cambridge vacuo-junction V.J. (Fig. 1). The source of light was a 200 watt incandescent (glass) bulb run at 200 volts, and placed at a distance of 25 cm. from the discharge tubes.

Oxygen, prepared and purified as described in Part I (Mohanty and Kamath, *loc. cit.*), was introduced into the semi-ozonisers at various p in the range of 10 to 450 mm.

* Outer diameter of the glass cylinder	5 mm.
Inner	4
Thickness of the glass wall	0.5
Diameter of the central H.T. electrode	0.25
Length of the electrode space	13.5 cm.

Hg in the case of W, and 150 to 450 mm. in the case of the other three semi-ozonisers. The gas was subjected to different alternating V varied over 0.5 to 4 kV (r.m.s.) of 50

FIG. 1.
Joshi effect in O_2 under semi-ozoniser excitation.

cycles frequency. Galvanometer deflections were noted in dark and under irradiation; from these, the discharge current in dark i_0 , that under irradiation i_x , the net effect Δi and the relative effect $\% \Delta i$ were calculated. The results are shown in Table I.

D I S C U S S I O N

It was shown earlier (Mohanty and Kamath, *loc. cit.*) that *ceteris paribus* V_m (defined as the minimum 'threshold potential' at which i increases rapidly with the applied V , and obtained by extrapolation of the $V-i_0$ characteristics) for oxygen subjected to alternating fields in Siemens' tubes was sensibly a linear function of p over a fairly wide range. That the pressure variation of V_m for the gas excited in semi-ozonisers is similar, except at comparatively low pressures, is evident from Fig. 2. V_m increases linearly from 0.69 kV at 100 mm. to 1.69 kV at 450 mm. Below 100 mm., V_m falls off more rapidly than p ; this might result from inaccuracy in fixing V_m for these pressures, since the $V-i$ characteristics are more horizontal.

The influence of the exciting V on Δi and $\% \Delta i$ in oxygen under semi-ozoniser excitation is similar to that observed for the gas in Siemens' tubes (Mohanty and Kamath, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE I (contd.)

Central H.T. V (kilo-volts i.m.s.)	Platinum										Gold			Silver			Copper			
	10	50	100	150	200	250	350	450	150	250	350	450	150	250	350	450	150	250	350	450
1.47	i_p	7.42	10.40	9.0	7.28	4.58			6.16	4.69			6.16	3.00			4.9	4.24		
	i_L	6.78	8.83	7.68	5.48	3.74			5.1	3.87			5.83	2.35			4.58	3.87		
	Δi	0.64	1.57	2.22	1.80	0.84			1.06	0.82			0.33	0.65			0.32	0.37		
	$\% \Delta i$	8.6	15.1	22.4	24.7	18.3			17.2	17.5			5.4	21.7			6.5	9.7		
1.6	i_p	3.87	7.75	11.09	10.95	8.31	6.48	1.73												
	i_L	3.46	7.07	9.54	8.54	6.16	4.9	1.00												
	Δi	0.41	0.68	1.55	2.41	2.15	1.58	0.73												
	$\% \Delta i$	10.6	8.8	14	22.0	25.9	24.4	42.2												
1.73	i_p	8.06	11.79	11.92	9.22	7.28	4.36		7.25	5.92	3.87		7.78	4.24	3.16		5.48	4.64	3.46	
	i_L	7.42	10.35	9.38	7.00	5.57	3.32		6.36	5.00	3.16		7.35	3.39	2.65		5.29	4.30	3.16	
	Δi	0.64	1.44	2.54	2.22	1.71	1.04		0.89	0.92	0.71		0.43	0.85	0.51		0.19	0.34	0.30	
	$\% \Delta i$	7.9	12.2	21.3	24.1	23.5	23.9		12.3	15.5	18.4		5.5	20.0	16.1		3.5	7.3	8.7	
1.87	i_p	4.12	8.31	12.46	12.76	10.10	8.00	6.08	5.1											
	i_L	3.74	7.68	11.00	10.10	7.68	6.25	4.69	4.00											
	Δi	0.38	0.63	1.46	2.66	2.42	1.75	1.39	1.1											
	$\% \Delta i$	9.2	7.6	11.7	20.8	24	21.9	22.9	21.6											
2	i_p	8.60	13.04	13.23	11.00	8.94	7.42	6.86	8.25	6.63	4.8	2.74	8.83	5.39	4.58	3.24	6.08	4.9	4.12	3.08
	i_L	8.00	11.58	10.58	8.37	7.07	5.75	5.39	7.42	5.61	3.87	2.45	8.31	4.53	3.74	2.83	5.92	4.69	3.74	2.83
	Δi	0.60	1.46	2.65	2.63	1.87	1.67	1.47	0.83	1.02	0.93	0.29	0.52	0.86	0.84	0.41	0.16	0.21	0.38	0.25
	$\% \Delta i$	7	11.2	20.0	23.9	20.9	22.5	21.4	10.1	15.4	19.4	10.6	5.9	16	18.3	12.7	2.6	4.3	9.2	8.1
2.13	i_p	4.53	8.83	13.68	14.18	11.88	9.85	8.43	8.72											
	i_L	4.12	8.19	12.21	11.53	9.17	7.75	6.48	6.93											
	Δi	0.41	0.64	1.47	2.65	2.71	2.10	1.95	1.79											
	$\% \Delta i$	9.1	7.2	10.8	18.7	22.8	21.3	23.1	20.5											
2.27	i_p	9.06	14.25	14.73	12.73	10.63	9.38	9.85	9.33	7.55	5.79	5.29	10.1	6.40	5.66	5.57	6.71	5.2	4.36	3.87
	i_L	8.43	12.80	12.28	10.00	8.43	7.28	7.81	8.60	6.40	4.8	4.24	9.54	5.57	4.69	4.36	6.56	5.00	4.00	3.54
	Δi	0.63	1.45	2.45	2.73	2.20	2.10	2.04	0.73	1.15	0.99	1.05	0.56	0.83	0.97	1.21	0.15	0.2	0.36	0.33
	$\% \Delta i$	7	10.2	16.6	21.05	20.7	22.4	20.7	7.8	15.2	17.1	19.9	5.5	13	17.1	21.7	2.2	3.8	8.3	10.7

TABLE I (contd.)

Central H. T. V (kilo-volts i.m.s.).	Platinum							Gold							Silver							Copper						
	10	50	100	150	200	250	350	450	150	250	350	450	150	250	350	450	150	250	350	450	150	250	350	450				
2.4	4.8	9.43	14.73	15.36	13.56	11.36	10.40	10.68	8.49	6.63	6.29		7.78	6.86	6.93		7.07	5.52	4.36	4.12								
	4.36	8.78	13.30	12.92	10.86	9.00	8.06	8.54	7.31	5.66	5.2		6.93	5.83	5.66		6.93	5.29	4.00	3.81								
	0.44	0.65	1.43	2.44	2.70	2.36	2.34	2.14	1.18	0.97	1.09		1.03	1.27			0.14	0.23	0.36	0.31								
	9.4	6.9	9.7	15.9	19.9	20.8	22.5	20.0	13.9	14.6	17.3		10.9	18.3			4.2	8.3	7.5									
2.53		9.75	15.36	16.06	14.39	12.17	11.36	11.45	10.63	6.63	6.29		11.53	6.86	6.93		7.07	5.52	4.36	4.12								
		9.11	14.01	13.56	11.66	9.8	8.83	9.17	10.00	7.31	5.2		11.23	6.93	5.66		6.93	5.29	4.00	3.81								
		0.64	1.35	2.50	2.73	2.37	2.53	2.28	0.63	1.18	0.97		0.30	1.03	1.27		0.14	0.23	0.36	0.31								
		6.6	8.8	15.6	19	19.5	22.3	19.9	5.9	13.9	14.6		2.6	15.0	18.3		2.2	4.2	8.3	7.5								
2.67		10.05	15.93	16.52	15.03	12.76	12.17	12.04																				
	5.1	4.69	9.43	14.56	14.07	12.37	10.44	9.49	9.7																			
	0.41	0.62	1.37	2.45	2.66	2.32	2.68	2.34																				
	8.0	6.2	8.6	14.8	17.7	18.2	22.0	19.4																				
2.8																												
3.07																												
3.33																												
3.6																												

FIG. 2

Variation with gas pressure p of the threshold potential, V_m for oxygen.

FIG. 3

Pressure variation of the Joshi effect in oxygen at const. i_D .

Δi sets in only near V_m . With V increased progressively beyond V_m , the net effect Δi increases to a maximum and then decreases (Table I). Thus *e.g.*, V_m at 150 mm. is 0.88 kV. At this pressure Δi sets in (1.00) at 0.93 kV, increases to a maximum of 2.65 at 2 kV, and falls off to 2.45 with further increase of V to 2.67 kV. Similar to results with Siemens' tubes (Mohanty and Kamath, *loc. cit.*), the applied V corresponding to maximum Δi increases with p . Thus, V for maximum Δi at 100 mm. is 1.33 kV; that at 150 mm. is 2 kV. Further, the increase of Δi is distributed over a wider range of V at higher than at low p . Thus *e.g.*, whilst at $pO_2=100$ mm., Δi increases over a range of 0.53 kV, it does so over 1.07 kV at 150 mm. The proportionate effect $\% \Delta i$ is maximum near V_m and diminishes with V . Thus, at 150 mm. ($V_m=0.88$ kV), $\% \Delta i$ sets in and is maximum (50.0) at 0.93 kV and diminishes to 14.8 at 2.67 kV.

FIG. 4

Influence of central H. T. on Joshi effect in O_2 under semi-ozonisers.

It is seen from Fig. 3 that Δi at constant i_D increases with p , at first rapidly and then slowly, to a maximum at $pO_2=200$ mm., followed by a slow decrease afterwards. Thus, for $i_D=7$, Δi at 50 mm. is 0.67. It increases to 1.5 at 100 mm., to 1.75 at 200 mm., and is reduced to 1.50 at 450 mm. The influence of p on Δi in oxygen (Mohanty and Kamath, *loc. cit.*), chlorine (Deo, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1945, Part III, *Phys.*

Sec., Abst. No. 13; Joshi and Deo, *Nature*, 1944, **163**, 434) and bromine (Rao, unpublished results) subjected to alternating fields in Siemens' tubes is similar.

The present experiments reveal that the magnitude of Δi in oxygen under semi-ozone excitation is markedly altered by a change in the material of the central H.T. electrode. At $pO_2=150$ mm. (Fig. 4), e.g., Δi at a given i_b varies in the order: Pt > Au > Ag > Cu; the effect with the last electrode is very small. At higher p , viz., 350 and 450 mm., Δi values with Au and Ag electrodes coincide within the limits of experimental error. This influence of the material of the central H.T. electrode on Δi is independent of the mode of current detection. Thus, the author and Pradhan (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1948, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 19) working with gold, silver and copper electrodes found that the effect observed with a diode used as half-wave detector varied in the same order.

According to Joshi (*ibid.*, 1946, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 26; 1947, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 25; *Curr. Sci.*, 1946, **16**, 281; 1947, **16**, 19), photo-electron emission from an adsorption-like ionic + molecular boundary layer formed on the electrodes under discharge, is primary to Δi . Oxygen is adsorbed chemically on Pt, Au, Ag and Cu (McBain, "The Sorption of Gases and Vapours by Solids", George Routledge, 1932, Chapter IX). Emission of photo-electrons from these metals is not possible under the light-band used, since the short-wave limit, viz., $3700\text{\AA}$ (Mohanty and Kamath, this *Journal*, 1948, **25**, 467) is higher than the threshold wavelengths of the metals, outgassed or not (Hughes and DuBridge, "Photoelectric Phenomena", McGraw-Hill, 1932, pp. 75, 76). Since the work-function, as also the spectral sensitivity of the boundary layers, will be different, variation in Δi is to be anticipated. The smoothness of the metallic surface is another consideration. A rough surface possesses a large area exposed to the gas; adsorption, and hence, Δi will be large.

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